

The policy guidance (E-Learning) of Commonwealth Educational Media Centre for Asia (CEMCA) Role of Netaji Subhas Open University

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Abstract

The Open University represents an alternative approach to higher learning. It stands apart from a highly formal, institutionalized and centrally administered system of education. Its philosophy is built around the principles of universality, flexibility and innovativeness. Its ideas and institutions, its methods and procedures are all shaped accordingly. Conceptually, it can be viewed as a system drawing upon the best elements in formal and non-formal education. The 'openness' consists of a variety of features.

1. It offers easy access to the learners. The entry requirement is not too exacting.
2. Its territorial reach is visibly wide. It aims at bringing education to the doorstep of the learner,
3. The Open University is learner-oriented. It devises its courses and methods of teaching to suit the needs of the learners.
4. It believes in fair distribution of quality education, teaching aid, consultancy and study materials.
5. Its administration is decentralized. In promoting Distance Education, the University creates a wide network of Study Centres.
6. Student assessment under Open University is based on continuous assessment and credit system. It does not require students to get bogged down in one final examination.

Distance education or long-distance learning is the education of students who may not always be physically present at a study centre. Today it involves online education. Courses that are conducted 100% distance learning. Massive open online courses (MOOCs), offering large-scale interactive participation and open access through the World Wide Web or other network technologies, are recent developments in distance education. Netaji Subhas Open University is the premier State Open University in India. A State Act (W.B. Act (XIX) of 1997 was the birth centenary year of Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose. and Recognised by U.G.C.) was passed on the 20th August 1997 in favour of opening a University for imparting Distance Education. It has its headquarters at 1, Woodburn Park, Kolkata - 700020, once the residence of Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose, leader of freedom fighter in India. Its medium of instruction is English and Bengali. Modelled on the Open University, UK and the IGNOU, it offers courses in different disciplines of taught graduate and post-graduate study and is one of the largest growing education universities in eastern India. It is the tenth Open University of the country and the ninth State Open University.

Keywords: Distance Learning Offers Individuals A Unique Opportunity To Benefit From The Expertise And E- Resources, E- Book, And Demand Of E-Resource For Learning In General Public.

Introduction

Commonwealth Educational Media Centre for Asia (CEMCA), CEMCA supported NSOU, Kolkata for the implementation of integrated higher education model in a project entitled "Increase Access and Improve Institutional Capacity for Sustainable Development through Vocational Education and Training". In this project, NSOU organized an outreach programme on the 2nd December, 2018 at Pranvananda Institute of Management and Technology (PIMT), A number of other terms (distributed learning, e-learning, online learning, virtual classroom etc.) are used

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roughly synonymously with distance education. Distance learning can also use interactive radio instruction (IRI), interactive audio instruction (IAI), online virtual worlds, digital games, webinars, and webcasts, all of which are referred to as e-Learning. CEMCA has been very closely associated with all aspects of development of Community Radio - Policy, Advocacy, Establishment of community radio stations and Capacity building for community engagement, station management as well as local content creation. CEMCA has developed a Community Learning Programme (CLP) model which is unique in its approach in bringing about Social Change using Community Media. The strategic objective of CEMCA is to promote co-operation and collaboration in the use of electronic media resources for distance education. The specific objectives are to:

1. Serve as a regional electronic media resource centre.
2. Facilitate an effective exchange of information on educational media resources between educational and media organisations in the region.
3. Promote greater use of electronic media in the delivery of distance education programmes.
4. Promote linkages between CEMCA and other organisations to enhance the availability of educational media resources region-wide
5. Facilitate access to training in the development and use of electronic media resources for distance education.
6. Serve as an information centre on educational technology.

The Asian regional meeting of COL Focal Points took place on the 10th - 11th December 2018 in New Delhi, India. The focus of the meeting was to strengthen the effectiveness of COL's strategic plan and programme activities in addressing the key priorities of Asian Commonwealth countries for education and training till 2021. CEMCA Announces EMFCA-18 were invited from individuals/ institutions that are the residents of one of the seven Commonwealth Countries in Asia, namely: Bangladesh, Brunei, India, Malaysia, Pakistan, Singapore and Sri Lanka. In this competition participants were send entries in one or more of the following categories, namely, Educational TV Programmes/ Documentaries, Educational e-Content with Multimedia, or Educational Platforms/ Applications. CEMCA's website at the following link: <http://cemca.org/in/> educational-media-festival-commonwealth CEMCA is organising the first "Educational Media Festival for Commonwealth Asia - 2018 (EMFCA18). This is an opportunity to get recognized for creating outstanding Educational TV Programmes, Documentaries, e-Content, Platforms and Applications.

Role of Netaji Subhas Open University

The first correspondence school in the United States was the Society to Encourage Studies at Home, which was founded in 1873. The Open University revolutionised the scope of the correspondence program and helped to create a respectable learning alternative to the traditional form

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of education. NSOU uses a variety of methods for distance learning:

1. Self Instructional Material: Self instructional study materials are distributed to the students through the Study Centres.
2. Audio-Video CD: Audio and video cassettes of a specific programme are supplied to the Study Centres. The audiotapes are run and video cassettes are screened at the Study Centres.
3. Personal Contact Programme: Instruction are imparted through self-instructional study materials and Personal Contact Programme. The Personal Contact Programme is generally held on Saturdays and Sundays.
4. Gyan Vani FM Channel: NSOU started the Gyan Vani FM, Kolkata, a radio channel on 105.4 MHz.
5. Interactive Radio Counselling: The University broadcasts different subjects on 4th Sunday of every month through All India Radio (AIR) at Kolkata B. Apart from the regular classes various topics on Awareness Programme; Support Services Special

Query of Access

Netaji Subhas Open University To provide individualised support to its students, NSOU has large number of Study Centres throughout West Bengal. To spread higher education in different parts of the state and to co-operate with other universities to provide access to higher education and to different skill enhancing educational programmes, Netaji Subhas Open University shall:

Provide quality education in a flexible mode to serve the aim of establishing an equitable knowledge society within the state; provide higher education through distance learning e-Resource.

1. About the learning management system
2. Video lectures on different subjects
3. Questions of different courses
4. Listing of E-resources under Consortium of Educational Communication (CEC), UGC
5. Video lectures on different subjects

Make Education Affordable To the Disadvantaged

1. Provide facility for lifelong education to intending learners
2. Strive for up gradation of technology without compromising the basic values of the society
3. Contribute to the development of the state and the nation and to motivate learners to strive for secular, scientific and democratic education.

Objective of the Study

The Open University represents an alternative approach to higher learning. Bringing education to the doorstep of the learner, wherever he or she may be. Various methods of communication and contact are used for this purpose. The classroom of the university, thus, is as wide as the entire land it seeks to serve. Third, the Open University is learner-oriented. It devises its course and methods of teaching to suit the needs of the learners.

Discussion and Conclusion

An open learning system is one in which the onus of learning is primarily on the students. Despite this, they are formally enrolled in a system which takes in other learners too. Thus, we draw a line of distinction between the above-mentioned category of students and those borrowing books from Libraries and those formally attached to a conventional university where classroom teaching is the principal mode of instruction. Distribution of quality education, teaching aid, consultancy and study materials. its administration is decentralized. In promoting Distance Education, the university creates a wide network of Study Centres, e-resource distribute with website , e-book, YouTube, Radio Class programme broadcasting in society .

Reference

- Andreas M.; Haenlein, Michael (2016). "Higher education and the digital revolution: About MOOCs, SPOCs, social media, and the Cookie Monster".
- Alan Tait. "Reflections on Student Support in Open and Distance Learning". *The International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*.
- Bizhan Nasseh. "A Brief History of Distance Education".
- Distance Education Accrediting Commission. "CHEA-Recognized Scope of

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Accreditation." "Archived copy". Archived from the original on 24 December 2016. Retrieved 4 November 2015.. April 2013.

Daniel, Sir John S (1998). *Mega-Universities and Knowledge Media: Technology Strategies for Higher Education*. Routledge. ISBN 0-7494-2634-9.

Honeyman, M; Miller, G (December 1993). "Agriculture distance education: A valid alternative for higher education?" (PDF). *Proceedings of the 20th Annual National Agricultural Education Research Meeting*: 67–73.

"History", University of London External Programme Website". *Londonexternal.ac.uk*. 15 July 2009. Retrieved 27 April 2010.

<http://www.cemca.org.in>

<http://www.wbnsou.ac.in>Kaplan,

Joseph F. Kett, *Pursuit of Knowledge Under Difficulties: From Self-Improvement to Adult Education in America* (1996) pp 236-8

Retrieved 2011-01-23.Cuban. (1986). *Teachers and Machines: The Classroom Use of Technology Since 1920*, pp 19–26

Tatum Anderson (16 May 2007). "History lessons at the people's university". *Guardianabroad.co.uk*. Archived from the original on 24 May 2007. Retrieved 20 September 2016.

Von V. Pittman, *Correspondence Study in the American University: A Second Historiographical Perspective*, in Michael Grahame Moore, William G. Anderson, eds. *Handbook of Distance Education* pp 21-36

White, Michael (2009). "Distance education in Australian higher education — a history". *Distance Education*. 3 (2): 255–78.